

THE DIFFERENCE BETWEEN HOTELS IN FOREIGN COUNTRIES

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Abstract. *This article presents hotels in foreign countries and hotel – related terms. Information such as how to get to the hotel and what internal rules apply to each hotel in each country is provided.*

Keywords: *Lobby, premium room, Reception, Reservation, Check – in, Check – out, Room service, Housekeeping, Booking.*

РАЗНИЦА МЕЖДУ ОТЕЛЯМИ В ЗАРУБЕЖНЫХ СТРАНАХ

Аннотация. *В этой статье представлены отели в зарубежных странах и термины, связанные с отелями. Предоставляется информация о том, как добраться до отеля и какие внутренние правила действуют в каждом отеле в каждой стране.*

Ключевые слова: *Лобби, номер премиум-класса, Ресепшн, Бронирование, Регистрация заезда, Регистрация отъезда, Обслуживание номеров, Уборка номеров, Бронирование.*

The hotel industry is one of the most widespread economies around the world. Each country describes how developed it is with the hotel economy and at the same time, the laws and regulations do not favor hotel accommodation.

1. European hotels.

Space is a valuable commodity in Europe. That's more evident in the capitals and other major cities rather than in rural areas. Europeans are used to living in smaller homes and staying in rather compact hotel rooms. However, for Americans, the size of the rooms can be a huge surprise. Especially, if it's your first time in Europe.

Whether your accommodation in Europe is housed in historic buildings or not, hotel rooms in Europe tend to be - a lot- smaller than in US, even within the same category regardless if it's 3 – or 5 – star hotel and no matter the room rate.

Believe it or not, it's not uncommon for the hotel chains you know your trips within North America to feature small rooms on the other side of the pond.

Inevitably, since hotel rooms in Europe are smaller than American hotel rooms, you should expect smaller beds, too. Contrary to most American hotels that often feature two double beds in the room, in Europe you'll either get one large bed or two single beds – sometimes referred to as twin beds – pushed together. If you ask for a third bed, it will most probably be a rollaway bed or a pull-out couch at an additional fee.

Since space is scarce, hotel bathrooms in Europe tend to be on the small side. Don't be surprised if it feels as though you can touch all bathroom walls from where you're standing, without even stretching your arms too far. You probably can. Another thing to keep in mind is that, with the exception of some 5-star luxury hotels, chances are you'll have a walk-in shower instead of a bathtub in your room.

One of the differences between American and European hotels that you might have never thought of has to do with how floors are numbered on either side of the Atlantic Ocean. As you know, in the US, a hotel lobby is on Level 1 and the rooms on the floor right above the lobby are considered to be on Level 2 (second floor).

However, in Europe, Level 1 is considered the first floor above the ground level. Therefore, a hotel lobby in Europe is usually on Level 0 and the rooms right above the lobby occupy the hotel's first floor. If there's a level below the lobby, that's Floor -1.

2. American hotels.

When guests walk into a hotel room, which amenities do they simply expect as part of a standard hotel experience? Which convey that they are in a premium or luxury hotel?

Wi-fi is the amenity expected by the most Americans, with 72% expecting it in any standard hotel room and 74% in any premium room. This is followed closely by toiletries (66% in standard v. 71% in premium). Moving down the list, the differences between different room grades becomes more apparent. In a premium room, guests are about twice as likely to expect personal care items such as combs and shower caps (60% v. 27%), room service (70% v. 32%) and mobile check-in (53% v. 25%) than they are in a standard room.

The items that most set the different room grades apart are the slippers and robe combo and the Bluetooth speaker. Only one-in-ten Americans expect slippers and robe in a standard room, but nearly six times more (58%) expect to find them in a premium room. While far fewer consumers expect a Bluetooth speaker, the ratio is about the same with 36% expecting to find one in a

premium room compared to only 7% in a standard room. This suggests that these items may evoke a luxury experience to guests. Conversely, if guests cannot wrap themselves in a plush hotel robe, they may feel that they're having a sub-premium experience.

For example, in premium hotel rooms, women have higher expectations than men by a significant margin in every category of amenity. Similarly, older consumers tend to have higher expectations than younger ones. The 55+ age group has the highest expectations in most categories. One exception is the Bluetooth speaker: 42% of 35-54-year-olds expect to see this in their premium room versus 32% of those aged 55+. When expectations are broken down by race, white people have the highest expectations across most categories. When it comes to in-room tablets, however, 31% of white consumers expect them, which is slightly below the average of 34%.

Putting these broad differences together, it may be that white women above the age of 55 are the most difficult consumers for hoteliers to please. The chart below, arranged by the difference between demographics shows that the in-room tablet is the only amenity for which this demographic has lower-than-average expectations.

3. Russian hotels.

The hotel industry does not function in a vacuum. It has to react to what happens outside the business. These factors are known as the factors of external and internal environment. The factors of internal environment consist of the factors onto which the hotel management can influence directly (for example standards of service, problems with staff, renovation of the hotel and etc.). The factors of external environment consist of factors of external environment of indirect (characteristics of society onto which the hotel management cannot influence directly but, however, they may have a decisive influence onto any further prospects) and direct (for example the situation with the clients, who would like some discounts, or loyal cards) effect. So, it means that the internal business environment includes factors within the organization that impact the approach and success of your operations. The external environment consists of a variety of factors outside your company doors that you typically don't have much control over.

At least the materials of study published on Federal Tourism Agency of the Ministry of Culture of the Russian Federation official website shows that after some economic instabilities in the country almost 80% of Russians decided to cut their cost on holidays. They prefer to stay at home. 17% is choosing the Russian Federation as the place for their holidays and only 3% plan to visit foreign countries.

Unfortunately, there are many different publications about the expensiveness of hotel services in Russia as well as about the noncompliance of prices and quality of services provided.

For example, according to the study of TripIndex Room Service 2013, Moscow was called the most expensive city. But now the situation is changing. Not surprisingly, Scandinavia emerged as the most expensive region on the index, with Nordic cities claiming four of the top 10 most expensive spots. After Helsinki, Oslo, Stockholm and Copenhagen also made the list. Moscow is not so expensive nowadays. At the same time, the situation with quality is changing. Many Russian and foreign people said that it become well.

Before going to any hotels, we need to learn some hotel-related terms:

Reception – a place where guests are upon arrival. This word reflects the basic meaning of service.

Reservation – advance booking process. This term is widely used in hotels practice.

Check – in - hotel check – in process

Check – out – hotel check – out process

Room service – guest’s room reservation

Housekeeping – providing a clean, comfortable, safe, and aesthetically appealing environment for guests

Booking – an agreement you have made to have a hotel room, tickets, etc. at a certain time in the future, or the process of implementing that agreement

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